

بیویوں کے مابین قسم: لسان الحکام فی معرفۃ الاحکام کی روشنی میں

Division Between Wives: In The Light of The Lisan ul AI-Hokaam Fi Ma'rifat Al-Ahkam

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Abstract

Islam stands as a harmonious faith, thoughtfully attuned to the intricacies of human psychology. It is not uncommon for scholars and observers from the East to raise concerns regarding the frequency of marriages in Islam, suggesting that it may inadvertently perpetuate gender oppression by permitting polygamy. Nevertheless, a closer examination reveals that this is not an avenue for oppression but rather a safeguard for modesty, with the very essence of marriage rooted in the preservation of virtue. The profound wisdom behind this allowance lies in the understanding that human desires can ebb and flow with changing circumstances, including variations in climate. In cases where these desires become overwhelming and there is no provision for a subsequent marriage, the question arises: why uphold the sanctity of modesty? Thus, Islam, emerging as a force to quell discord, vice, and societal turmoil, has extended the privilege of entering into up to four marriages simultaneously. It is crucial to underline that this permission comes with stringent conditions, articulated in the realm of Islamic jurisprudence as 'Qasam'.

Keywords: Polygamy, Faith, Marriages, Preservation, Islamic Jurisprudence

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